

Language Use In Communication By Ethnic Minority People In Dong Nai Province, Vietnam

Hoat Nguyen, Phuong Vu

Article Info

Article History

Received:
November 10, 2024

Accepted:
February 10, 2025

Keywords :

Language Use,
Communication, Ethnic
Minorities, Dong Nai,
Mother Tongue,
Vietnamese

Abstract

Language is a means of communication and expression of thinking. Human cognitive level, identity and culture of the nation are shown through voice and script. The issue of using language in communication in ethnic minority areas is an important content for the promulgation of a country's language policy. The article examines the language use in communication by ethnic minority people in Dong Nai province, Vietnam in terms of: language use in family and in society. The research results clarify the level of using the mother tongue and Vietnamese language by ethnic minority people in the area, which will help the government issue suitable policies to facilitate their use of language to acquire knowledge, develop the economy, integrate with modern life and contribute to the preservation of cultural values of the community.

DOI:

10.5281/zenodo.14845648

Introduction

Dong Nai Province is located in the Southern Key Economic Region of Vietnam [2], covering an area of 5,907.2 km². It is bordered by Binh Thuan province to the East, Binh Duong Province and Ho Chi Minh City to the West, Ba Ria – Vung tau to the South, Lam Dong and Binh Phuoc province to the North. Dong Nai holds a very important position as it is the eastern gateway to Ho Chi Minh City and thus, a major economic center of the south, connecting the South Central region and South Central Highlands to the entire Southeast region [3]. Bien Hoa, the capital city of Dong Nai Province, is the most populous provincial city located about 30 kilometres from Ho Chi Minh City and 1,684km from Hanoi following National Highway No.1A.

At the time of the April 2019 Census, the population of Dong Nai Province stands at 3,097,107 [1, p.159] with 54 ethnic groups. Among them are Kinh people (2,311,315 people, comprising 92.96%), other ethnic minorities (174,839 people, comprising 7.04%). Some ethnic minorities with a population of more than 1,000 are: Chinese (95,162 people), Nung (19,076 people), Tay (15,906 people), Cho Ro (15,174 people), Khmer (7,059 people), Muong (5,337 people), Dao (4,717 people), Cham (3,887 people), Ma (2,436 people), Xtieng (1,269 people) and Thai (1,190 people). Other ethnic minority groups include: San Diu, Co Ho, Tho, Ede, San Chay... [8]

This study examines the issue of using languages in communication by ethnic minority people in Dong Nai Province. Based on the survey into the linguistic competence in ethnic collaborators' mother tongue and Vietnamese, the research will shed light on the language use of ethnic minority people in family and in society. The use of language within a family refers to the communication: with other family members, with visitors from the same ethnic group and from other ethnic minorities. The language use in the society refers to the communication: in meetings at administrative units or civil social organizations, in the workplace, through telephones, and in some other contexts.

Research subjects

Data were collected from 306 collaborators including 156 males and 150 females who are ethnic minority people in Dong Nai Province. They come from 3 different administrative divisions: 119 participants from Xuan Dinh Commune, Xuan Loc District; 106 participants from Tan Phu Town, Tan Phu District; and 81 participants from Phuoc Tan Ward, Bien Hoa City. Their age range, occupation and education level are presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Research subjects

Administrative divisions (quantity)	Quantity
Xuan Dinh Commune, Xuan Loc District	119
Tan Phu Town, Tan Phu District	106
Phuoc Tan Ward, Bien Hoa City	81

Quantity (gender);	306 (156 males; 150 females)										
Quantity (Age range)	5 (<18); 30 (19-30); 138 (31-50); 133 (≥ 51)										
Occupation/ Quantity	Farmers	Students	Other occupations	Workers	Merchants	Working in the Service Industry	Working in the Armed forces	Commune officer	Provincial officers	Retirees	
	663	6	3	10	6	4	1	1	3	9	
Educational level/ Quantity											
Illiterate	Primary school			Secondary school		High school		Undergraduate			
7	182			88		18		11			

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

Xuan Loc District, located in the South and Southeast region of Dong Nai Province, borders Binh Thuan Province. Gia Ray Town is 74 kilometres away from Bien Hoa City and 96 kilometres from Ho Chi Minh City. The population of the district is 205,547 people with 50 ethnic groups residing in the whole region. Among them are Kinh people (188,118 people, comprising 91.52%) and other ethnic minorities (17,429 people, comprising 8.48%). Some ethnic groups with a population of more than 1,000 are: Chinese (5,236 people), Cho ro (4,508 people), Cham (2,119 people), Tay (1,627 people), and Nung (1,500 people). Other ethnic minorities include: Khmer, Dao, Xtieng, Muong,...

 [8]

Tan Phu District, located in the North and Northeast region of Dong Nai Province, borders Lam Dong Province. Tan Phu Town is 110 kilometres northeast of Bien Hoa City and 140 kilometres from Ho Chi Minh City. There are 155,926 people with 50 ethnic groups residing in the whole region. Among them are Kinh people (142,441 people, comprising 91.35%) and other ethnic minorities (13,485 people, comprising 8.65%). Some ethnic groups with a population of more than 1,000 are: Chinese (7,216 people), Tay (2,009 people), and Ma (1,304 people). Other ethnic minorities include: Khmer, Nung, Muong, Thai...

 [8]

Bien Hoa City, located in the West and Southwest region of Dong Nai Province, borders Binh Duong Province and Ho Chi Minh City. It is 30 kilometres away from the centre of Ho Chi Minh City and 90 kilometres from Vung Tau City. There are 1,099,943 people with 53 ethnic groups residing in the whole region. Among them are Kinh people (1,087,363 people, comprising 98.85%) and other ethnic minorities (12,580 people, comprising 1.15%). Some ethnic groups with a population of more than 1,000 are: Chinese (6,164 people), Nung (1,754 people), Tay (1,502 people), and Khmer (1,137 people). Other ethnic minorities include: Muong, Thai, Tho, Cham...

 [8]

Methodology

Based on the analysis of geographical features together with demographic data and ethnic composition in the region of Dong Nai Province, a questionnaire of 30 items related to the research content was designed. The researcher observed all legal formalities, organized human resources for the field trip and directly contacted research subjects. The participants were then instructed to complete the questionnaire by ticking from the given options. Intensive note-taking and in-depth interviews were employed to answer research questions.

Afterward, the questionnaires were collected and classified; their results were then analyzed and calculated in percentage terms for each item before a statistical table was made based on the questions. The data from the survey were compared to those from previous interviews conducted among participants, from activities of residents in the region, and from local authorities at different levels ranging from villages to districts, communes and the province. The results were also compared to related documents to ensure that these figures are objective and accurate.

Results and Discussion

Linguistic competence

Speaking and writing competence in the mother tongue

The concept of mother tongue is quite complex as being proposed by many researchers in varied ways. According to Nguyen Thien Giap, a mother tongue 'is the first language that a person acquires from birth' [4, p.309]. The first language that a person acquires is usually mother tongue which means the language of one's ethnic group. However, in reality, there exist a lot of cases in which the first language a child acquires from birth is not the language of his ethnic group. For instance, the child's parents cannot use their mother tongue because they have been living in a different ethnic community; or the child was born and raised in a different environment where he is not exposed to the language of his ethnic group; or the wife or the husband is from a

different ethnic group and thus, may live in a region with a different mother tongue. In the aforementioned cases, the child will be able to use the country's official language and another language of the ethnic group he is living with.

As a result, in this research content, the term 'mother tongue' refers to the language of the ethnic group which a participant belongs to. In case the participants come from different ethnic minorities, the dominant language with the highest number of ethnic users in the region would be considered the mother tongue of participants listed in the table in contrast with Vietnamese and other language patterns used in communication.

Table 2. Linguistic competence of participants

Options	Mother tongue		Vietnamese		Language of other ethnic group (1)		Language of other ethnic group (2)		Foreign language (English)	
	Speaking	Writing	Speaking	Writing	Speaking	Writing	Speaking	Writing	Speaking	Writing
Incompetence	3	72	3	6	50	49				
Little competence	20	28	20	122	2				1	1
Average competence	259	18	246	138	1	1				
Number of respondents	282	118	269	266	53	50	0	0	1	1
Multiple responses	17		19	4		4				
No response	7	188	18	36	253	253	306	306	305	305
Total	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

Table 2 shows speaking competence of participants in their mother tongue with the response from 282/306 people (comprising 92.15%). Among them, there are 259/282 participants (91.84%) using their mother tongues in communication, which confirms the fact that the majority of ethnic minority people in Dong Nai Province mostly gather in villages where the mother tongue still plays an important role in promoting cultural values of the community. However, as some families inhabit far away from their home villages and thus, have few opportunities to be exposed to their mother tongue, the level of using this language among them is reducing: the number of respondents who can speak a little mother tongue was 20 out of 282 (7.09%) while 3 out of 282 respondents (1.06%) can not speak it at all. This may indicate a tendency among a part of ethnic population in the region to be unable to use their mother tongue in communication, rendering the language at risk of disappearing in the future.

Regarding writing competence in the mother tongue, there are 118/306 participants (comprising 38.56%) responding to the interview. Among them, 72/118 respondents (61.02%) can not write their native language. This figure was much higher compared to the proportion of ethnic people who were incompetent to speak their mother tongue. The causes can be varied and dependent on many factors including most participants not having a chance to learn to write in their mother tongue at school, in family or in society, which means that the written language of ethnic minorities in the region is in danger of extinction. 28/118 respondents (comprising 23.37%) can write a little mother tongue while 18/118 respondents (15.25%) can write it fluently. This reflects a small proportion of participants being competent to write their mother tongue. Therefore, it is essential to implement practical measures to preserve, conserve and promote the value of written language among ethnic minority people in the modern world.

Speaking and writing competence in Vietnamese

Table 2 shows speaking competence of participants in Vietnamese with the response from 268/306 people (comprising 87.58%). A majority of them, 246/268 respondents (91.79%), are competent to speak Vietnamese, which confirmed an important position of Vietnamese language in the social life of ethnic minority people in particular and of people in the whole country in general. Ethnic minority people use Vietnamese in spoken communication with Vietnamese people and other ethnic minority people in the community. Nevertheless, there

is a small proportion of participants who can speak a little Vietnamese (20/268 respondents comprising 7.46%) and 3/268 respondents (accounting for 1.12%) can not speak Vietnamese at all. These participants were mostly at the age of above 60 and several of them were illiterate due to their plight. They did not go to school and had little contact with Kinh people. These figures indicate that the government at all levels in the region needs to facilitate learning Vietnamese so that ethnic minority people will be able to use this national language for community integration.

Regarding writing competence in Vietnamese, there are 266/306 participants (89.93%) responding to the interview. Among them, 138/266 respondents (51.88%) can write Vietnamese fluently; 122/266 respondents (45.68%) can write a little Vietnamese whereas 6/266 respondents (15.25%) can not write Vietnamese at all. Compared to the proportion of respondents who were able to write their mother tongue at both levels of average competence and little competence (46/118 respondents comprising 38.98%), the percentage of those who can write Vietnamese is much higher (260/266 people comprising 97.74%). However, the number of ethnic minority people who can write just a little Vietnamese and who can not write any Vietnamese at all was clearly substantial. This implies that their Vietnamese proficiency is still low as a lot of ethnic minority people in the region have no access to formal education and thus, no chance to communicate with Kinh people, which leads to their illiteracy in this language.

In addition to the speaking and writing competence in their mother tongue and in Vietnamese, there are 3/53 respondents (5.66%) who can speak the language of other ethnic groups and 1/50 respondents (2%) who can write it. As for foreign language (English), only 1/306 participants (0.32%) can speak and write it. These figures show low proficiency in the language of other ethnic groups and in foreign language among the participants.

Language use in communication in family and in society

Language use in communication in family

The participants were surveyed about their choice of language use in communication in family regarding: communication at home with other family members, communication at home with visitors from the same ethnic group, communication at home with visitors from other ethnic groups. The age range of participants includes: under 18, from 19 to 30, from 31 to 50 and above 51. The options for language use involve: their mother tongue, Vietnamese, mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese, mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue, and mainly mother tongue with some language of other ethnic minorities. The detailed figures are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Language use in communication in family according to ages of respondents

Options	Communication at home with other family members				Communication at home with visitors from the same ethnic group				Communication at home with visitors from other ethnic groups			
	<18	19-30	31-50	≥ 51	<18	19-30	31-50	≥ 51	<18	19-30	31-50	≥ 51
Mother tongue	31	94	132	134	28	89	123	120	10	10	12	11
Vietnamese	120	56	20	21	128	67	35	35	266	270	268	268
Mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese	50	52	51	48	47	49	44	45	3	2	1	1
Mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue	10	8	8	5	5	6	8	8	2	2	2	2
Mainly mother tongue with some language of other ethnic minorities	5	5	6	6	5	5	5	5	1	10		2
Number of respondents	216	215	217	214	213	216	215	213	282	294	283	284
Multiple responses	76	81	81	75	73	76	80	74	3	12	10	3
No response	14	10	8	17	20	14	11	19	21	10	13	19
Total	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

Language use in communication at home with other family members

Communication within the family mainly occurs between the respondents and other family members who belong to the same ethnic group. There exist some cases in which the wife and the husband come from a different ethnic group or one of the spouses is an ethnic getting married with a Kinh person. A detailed description of the number and proportion of participants making different choices about language use in communication at home with other family members is given below according to their age range:

Under 18 age range: There were 216/306 participants (comprising 70.59%) responding to the interview. At this age range, the percentage of respondents who used Vietnamese to communicate with other family members accounted for the highest proportion (120/216 respondents comprising 55.55%) compared to the use of other languages. This reflects a fact that most participants were of school age when they can acquire Vietnamese and therefore had a lot of opportunities to use Vietnamese in communication with the community. Regarding the way participants use language in communication, the results are: mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese (50/216 respondents comprising 23.15%); their mother tongue only (31/216 comprising 14.35%). Other language use made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (10/216 respondents comprising 4.63%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (5/216 respondents comprising 2.31%).

19-30 age range: There were 215/306 participants (comprising 70.26%) responding to the interview. Most of them are breadwinners in the family. Mainly working as farmers, they communicate with other family members using their mother tongue. Therefore, mother tongue was the most favourite option (94/215 respondents comprising 43.72%). Due to the needs for imparting scientific information and news and for socializing in modern life, 56/215 participants (comprising 26.04%) at this age range also used Vietnamese to communicate with other family members. As there were some family members coming from Kinh or other ethnic groups, the whole family opted to use Vietnamese for communication. Other language use made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (8/215 comprising 3.72%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (5/215 comprising 2.32%).

31-50 age range: There were 217/306 participants (comprising 70.91%) responding to the interview. In their middle age years, except for a few of them actively joining in social activities, most were bound to villages and cultivated fields. Therefore, their mother tongue was the most-used language among 132/217 respondents (comprising 60.83%) to communicate with other family members. Also, due to the needs for social integration and information exchange in the modern world, 51/217 respondents (comprising 23.50%) at this age range mainly used mother tongue in combination with Vietnamese in order to connect with the community and have access to a wider society. Compared to other younger age groups, the frequency of using Vietnamese by respondents of this age range was lower with only 20/217 users (comprising 9.21%). Other language use made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (8/217 comprising 3.68%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (6/217 comprising 2.76%).

Over 51 age range: There were 214/306 participants (comprising 69.93%) responding to the interview. At this age range, most respondents lead a stable life with their families, having little communication with the outside world. Hence their mother tongue was the most favorite choice among 134/217 respondents (comprising 26.61%) to communicate with other family members; the second-most used way of communication chosen by 48/214 respondents (comprising 22.43%) was mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese. The use of Vietnamese only was chosen by 21/214 participants (comprising 9.81%). Other language use made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (5/214 respondents comprising 2.33%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (6/214 respondents comprising 2.80%).

The results revealed the most-used languages according to age ranges including: Vietnamese with 120/216 users (comprising 55.55%) under 18 years old, mother tongue with 94/215 users (comprising 43.72%) from 19-30 years old, mother tongue with 132/217 users (comprising 60.83%) from 31-50 years old, and mother tongue with 134/214 users (comprising 26.61%) over 51 years old. Vietnamese is the most common answer from the under 18 age group, which indicates that the percentage of participants using Vietnamese is inversely proportional to the age range. This means that the younger the participants are, the higher their Vietnamese proficiency is. Conversely, the older the participants are, the lower their Vietnamese proficiency would be. This

is probably due to the fact that communicative needs in family and in society can affect one's competence in Vietnamese.

Regarding the mother tongue, there were high proportions of participants from the three age groups, namely 19-30 years old, 31-50 years old and above 51 years old, using it to communicate with family members. This reveals the importance of mother tongue in the family life of participants. The most-used language for communication among family members was mother tongue with the total of 391/862 users (comprising 43.36%) while the second most-used one was Vietnamese with the total of 217/862 votes (comprising 25.17%) from all age groups. Another aspect to consider is the language pattern with the most popular choice being the combination of mainly mother tongue and some Vietnamese (201/862 users comprising 23.31%). According to the row statistics in *Table 3.1.*, *the proportion of participants using their mother tongue positively correlated with their age.* This means, the older they are, the more frequently they use mother tongue in family communication. For instance, the frequency of using mother tongue in the age of under 18 was 31/391 (7.93%), in the age range from 19 to 30 was 94/391 (24.04%), in the age range from 31-50 was 132/391 (33.76%) and above 51 was 134/391 (34.27%). Accordingly, this revelation is contrasted with the aforementioned trend in using Vietnamese to communicate among family members.

The three patterns of language use in family communication include mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese, mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue, and mainly mother tongue with some language of other ethnic minorities. A high percentage of participants from the three age groups used mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese, especially in those families with some members who cannot speak Vietnamese or with some members who cannot speak their mother tongue but can speak Vietnamese.

Language use in communication at home with visitors from the same ethnic group

Under 18 age range: There were 213/306 participants (comprising 69.60%) responding to the interview. At this age range, these respondents have a lot of opportunities to acquire and access new knowledge, and to engage in wider communication. Although visitors were from the same ethnic group, they were at the same age with the participants and were inhibited from using their mother tongue. Therefore, most participants used the national language which is Vietnamese to communicate at the highest proportion (128/213 comprising 60.10%). The proficiency in the mother tongue of visitors would decide the patterns of language which were mainly mother tongue combined with some Vietnamese chosen by 47/213 respondents (comprising 22.06%), or only mother tongue chosen by 28/213 respondents (comprising 13.14%). Other language use patterns made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (5/213 comprising 2.34%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (5/213 comprising 2.34%).

19-30 age range: There were 216/306 participants (comprising 70.59%) responding to the interview. With similar ethnicity, most visitors and participants at this age range have finished schooling and thus, had certain experience in life and in language use to communicate and socialize with the community in the modern world. At the same time, in order to assert their own ethnic identity through the mother tongue and to build a rapport in community communication, 89/216 participants (comprising 41.20%, which is the highest number) used their native language to communicate with visitors from the same ethnic group at home. The second highest proportion was from the use of Vietnamese with 67/216 respondents (comprising 31.02%) and mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese chosen by 49/216 respondents (comprising 22.68%). Other language use patterns made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (6/216 comprising 2.77%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (5/216 comprising 2.31%).

31-50 age range: There were 215/306 participants (comprising 70.26%) responding to the interview. As presented in the previous section (3.1.1), there was a correlation between the frequency of using mother tongue with the age of participants. Thus, 123/215 respondents (comprising 57.21%, the highest proportion) chose their mother tongue when communicating with visitors from the same ethnic group. At this age range, they are competent enough to assert their own ethnic minority and have plenty of experience to use the language effectively in communication with in-group visitors at home. The proficiency in the mother tongue of visitors would also decide the patterns of language which were mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese chosen by 44/215 participants (comprising 20.46%), or only Vietnamese chosen by 35/215 participants (comprising 16.28%). Other language use patterns made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue (8/215 comprising 3.72%) and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities (5/215 comprising 2.32%).

Over 51 age range: There were 213/306 participants (comprising 69.60%) responding to the interview. At this age range, most respondents were leading a stable life with their families. Their life experience was rich and they were able to use appropriate language to communicate with visitors from the same ethnic group. Therefore, the languages in the order of popularity included: mother tongue chosen by 120/213 participants comprising 56.34%, mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese chosen by 45/213 participants comprising 21.12%, Vietnamese chosen by 35/213 participants comprising 16.43%, mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue chosen by 8/213 participants comprising 3.75% and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities chosen by 5/213 participants comprising 2.34%.

In general, most participants under 18 years old tend to use Vietnamese when communicating with visitors from the same ethnic group for social integration in modern life. Participants from the three age groups including 19-30, 31-50 and above 51 years old prioritize their mother tongue over other languages. Following their mother tongue, the language pattern of using mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese was chosen by the age groups of under 18, from 31 to 50 and above 51 years old. Only the group of participants from 19 to 30 years old prioritize Vietnamese in addition to their mother tongue. Other language use patterns made up an insignificant proportion, including: mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue, and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities.

According to the comparison shown in Table 3.1, the most-used language for communication with visitors from the same ethnic group was mother tongue with the total of 360/857 votes (comprising 42%), the highest figures among the age groups. This reveals *a positive correlation between the frequency of using mother tongue and the age of participants*. For instance, the frequency of using mother tongue among participants at the age of under 18 was 28/360 (7.77%), in the age range from 19 to 30 was 89/360 (24.72%), in the age range from 31-50 was 123/360 (34.16%) and above 51 was 120/360 (33.33%). The second most-used language in this scenario is Vietnamese with the total of 265/857 votes (comprising 31%). However, *the older participants are, the less frequent they use Vietnamese*. For instance, the frequency of using Vietnamese among participants at the age of under 18 was 128/265 (40.30%), in the age range from 19 to 30 was 67/265 (25.28%), in the age range from 31-50 was 35/265 (13.20%) and above 51 was 35/265 (13.20%). Other language patterns just accounting for an inconsiderable proportion of users included mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue, and mainly mother tongue with some languages of other ethnic minorities.

Language use in communication at home with visitors from other ethnic groups

The proportions of participants responding to the interview according to age ranges are: 282/306 subjects under 18 years old (92.15%), 294/306 subjects from 19 to 30 years old (96.08%), 283/306 subjects from 31-50 years old (92.48%) and 284/306 subjects above 51 years old (92.81%). Visitors come from a different ethnic group which might be Kinh or other ethnic minorities. Therefore, in order to have effective communication, Vietnamese as the national language was mainly used. For instance, the proportions were 266/282 (94.32%) among respondents under 18 years old, 270/294 (91.83%) among those who were 19 to 30 years old, 268/283 (94.7%) among those who were 31 to 50 years old and 268/284 (94.36%) among those above 51 years old.

However, in some special circumstances when neither participants nor visitors are competent in Vietnamese, other language patterns should be employed so that they can communicate with each other. For instance, they can opt for mother tongue of participants or of visitors, mainly mother tongue of participants or of visitors with some Vietnamese, mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue of participants or of visitors, and mainly mother tongue of participants or of visitors with some languages of other ethnic minorities. Nevertheless, these forms of language use just accounted for a small proportion of choice.

According to the comparison of the rows in Table 3.1, below are the results in the order of popularity among participants from each age group: Vietnamese with 1,072/1,143 respondents (93.79%), mother tongue of participants or of visitors with 43/1,143 respondents (3.76%), mainly mother tongue of participants or of visitors combined with some languages of other ethnic minorities with 13/1,143 respondents (1.13%); mainly Vietnamese combined with some mother tongue of participants or of visitors with 8/1,143 respondents (0.7%), and mainly mother tongue of participants or of visitors with some Vietnamese with 7/1,143 respondents (0.61%).

Language use in communication in society

One of communication forms in society is using languages to convey information in the following scenarios: participating in meetings at different levels such as those in villages, communes, districts, provinces... and

conferences organized by some union organization like Association of Vietnamese Elders, Youth Union, Pioneers' Organization, using languages to communicate in the workplace and in some public places like markets, docks, stores, festivals or tourism places, and using languages in telephone communication and in some other cases.

Language use in meetings

Language use patterns in meeting communication include: Vietnamese, mother tongue, mainly mother tongue combined with some Vietnamese, and mainly Vietnamese combined with some mother tongue. The use of mother tongue in meetings at administrative units and civil society organizations is preferred when there is a majority ethnic group using that language to communicate in the region.

Table 4. Language use in meeting communication

Language use patterns	Communication in meetings						
	In villages	In communes	In districts	In provinces	For elders	For youth	For pioneers
Vietnamese	264	295	259	255	260	265	260
Mother tongue	11	2	1	1	1	1	1
Mainly mother tongue with some Vietnamese	1	1			1		
Mainly Vietnamese with some mother tongue	1						
Number of respondents	277	298	260	256	262	266	261
Multiple responses	8	1			1	1	1
No response	21	7	46	50	43	39	44
Total	306	306	306	306	306	306	306

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

Table 4 shows the proportions of participants responding to the interview about their language use as follows: in villages' meetings: 277/306 respondents (90.52%), in communes' meetings: 298/306 respondents (97.38%), in districts' meetings: 260/306 respondents (84.96%), in provinces' meetings: 256/306 respondents (83.66%), in elders' meeting: 262/306 (85.62%), in youth meetings: 266/306 respondents (86.93%), in pioneers' meetings: 261/306 respondents (85.29%). The most-used language in those meetings was Vietnamese with details below:

In meetings at different levels of administrative units, the numbers of participants using Vietnamese were: in villages: 264/277 respondents (95.30%), in communes: 295/298 respondents (98.99%), in districts: 259/260 respondents (99.61%), in provinces: 255/256 respondents (99.61%). Meetings at administrative units and civil society organizations in the region where ethnic minority people live usually include a lot of officers from different positions, age ranges, genders, and ethnic groups. They can be: local people, people assuming related positions, senior delegates or invited delegates from other units... For that reason, in order to convey information, discuss the content of the meeting and exchange with each other, the chairman and other participants need to use Vietnamese, the national language. The survey results show that the frequency of using Vietnamese among participants when they were in administrative meetings was above 95% and this figure increased gradually in accordance with the level from villages to provinces. The percentage of respondents using Vietnamese in meetings of civil society organizations reached 99%.

However, when joining community meetings, some participants with limited fluency in Vietnamese used their mother tongue instead. For instance, 11/277 (3.97%) respondents used their mother tongue in villages' meetings and 2/298 (0.68%) did so in communes' meetings. Alternatively, they used other language patterns in communication such as mainly mother tongue combined with some Vietnamese or mainly Vietnamese combined with mother tongue. These cases accounted for a minor proportion, just 1%.

Language use in communication in the workplace and public places

Figures from Table 5 specifically show the workplace and public places where participants use different language patterns like Vietnamese, languages of other ethnic minorities, or Vietnamese combined with mother tongue to communicate with Kinh people, people from the same or from other ethnic groups. Some public places listed in the survey include markets, docks, stores, visitors, sightseeing places...

Table 5. Language use in communication in the workplace and public places

Language use patterns	Places of communication											
	Workplace			Public places								
	Kinh	Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	Markets			Docks, stores			Festival, sightseeing places		
Kinh				Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	Kinh	Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	Kinh	Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	
Vietnamese	299	180	290	301	71	294	297	66	294	298	66	296
Mother tongue		93		1	111	2	2	109	3	2	107	2
Languages of other ethnic groups					2	1					3	
Vietnamese and mother tongue		13	2		63	2		69		2	67	
Number of respondents	299	214	292	302	247	299	299	244	297	302	243	298
Multiple responses	2	9	2	1	53		3	54	1		52	
No response	5	11	12	3	6	7	4	8	8	4	11	8
Total	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

Table 5 reveals the proportions of participants using language patterns in communication in the workplace and public places as follows:

The use of Vietnamese: There were high proportions, above 93%, of respondents using Vietnamese to communicate with Kinh people and people from other ethnic groups as follows: communication in the workplace with Kinh people: 299/299 respondents (100%), with people from other ethnic minorities: 290/292 respondents (99.31%); communication in public places, such as *at markets*, with Kinh people: 301/293 respondents (99.67%), with people from another ethnic minorities: 294/299 respondents (98.32%); *at docks or stores*, with Kinh people: 297/299 respondents (99.33%), with people from another ethnic minorities: 294/297 respondents (99.00%); *at festivals or sightseeing places*: with Kinh people: 298/302 respondents (98.67%), with people from another ethnic minorities: 296/298 respondents (99.33%). This displays a national position of Vietnamese in life generally and in the workplace particularly, not only for Kinh people but also for people from different ethnic minorities.

In the context of communication between participants and people sharing the same ethnic group, Vietnamese was less used as they opted for their mother tongue or a combination of Vietnamese and mother tongue when conversing with each other in the workplace or public places. For instance, the proportion of participants using Vietnamese in communication: in the workplace was 180/286 respondents (62.93%); in public places such as *at markets* was 71/247 respondents (28.74%), *at docks or stores* was 66/244 respondents (27.05%), and *at festivals or sightseeing places* was 66/243 respondents (27.16%).

The use of mother tongue: Among people sharing the same ethnicity, when communicating in the workplace and public places, besides Vietnamese as the national language, they also use their mother tongue to exchange information and express emotions. The use of mother tongue gives listeners great comfort as it is easy to

understand, memorize and bring about sympathy and empathy. Additionally, using mother tongue can be a habit or inspiration creating fellowship and ethnic minority through their own native language they use to communicate with each other. The proportions of people from the same ethnic group using mother tongue in communication in the workplace and public places were: in the workplace 93/286 (32.51%); at markets 111/247 (44.94%), at docks or stores 109/244 (44.67%), and *at festivals or sightseeing places* 107/243 (44.03%).

The language use pattern of Vietnamese combined with mother tongue: This is a form of expression which employs alternately and simultaneously Vietnamese and the mother tongue of major ethnic people or the native language of a particular ethnic minority in the region (when both speakers and listeners are able to understand the same language of communication). This language use pattern, besides being relevant to those who are competent in Vietnamese, is applicable to some participants who are not fluent in Vietnamese but proficient in their own mother tongue or the native language of a major ethnic group in the region. The proportions of respondents using Vietnamese combined with their mother tongue to communicate with people from the same ethnicity were as follows: in the workplace 13/286 (4.54%); in public places such as at markets 63/247 (25.50%), at docks or stores 69/244 (28.28%), and at festivals or sightseeing places 67/243 (27.57%). These figures show that the language use of Vietnamese combined with their mother tongue in communication among people from the same ethnicity was more popular in public places than in the workplace. Other language use patterns only accounted for an insignificant proportion of respondents.

Language use in telephone communication and in some other settings

The language use patterns in telephone communication and some other contexts include Vietnamese, mother tongue, languages of other ethnic minorities and Vietnamese combined with ethnic languages. Mobile phones are popular means of communication due to their convenience in daily life of people in general and of ethnic minority people in particular. The language use in telephone communication demonstrates clearly the competence and literacy of the locals. Other forms of using language through telephone include calling and texting between respondents and Kinh people, people with the same ethnicity and in intergroup settings. Other contexts include lulling a baby to sleep, talking to themselves and singing. The survey results are shown through *Table 6*.

Table 6. Language use in telephone communication and in some other settings

Language use patterns	Telephone communication			Texting			Other settings		
	Kinh	Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	Kinh	Same ethnicity	Different ethnicity	Lulling	Self-talking	Singing
Vietnamese	300	76	297	301	208	298	81	55	245
Mother tongue	1	103			69		91	186	12
Languages of other ethnic groups		6			5		96	36	27
Vietnamese and mother tongue		63	2		8				
Number of respondents	301	248	299	301	290	298	268	277	284
Multiple responses		49			1		15	5	13
No response	5	9	7	5	15	8	23	24	9
Total	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306	306

(Source: Survey results from field work by the research team between October 2019 and April 2020)

The results from the survey on language use patterns in communication of respondents texting and calling were as follows:

The use of Vietnamese made up large proportions in these cases: when making a phone call with: Kinh people (300/301 accounting 99.66%), people from other ethnic groups (297/299 comprising 99.33%); when sending text messages to: Kinh people (301/301 comprising 100%), people from other ethnic groups 298/298 (100%). In communication with people sharing the same ethnicity through texting and calling, Vietnamese use accounts for smaller proportion compared to the cases with Kinh people and people from other ethnic groups, for instance, when making a phone call: 76/248 comprising 30.64%, when sending text messages: 208/290 comprising 71.72%. This is probably due to the fact that besides using Vietnamese, those respondents are competent in their mother tongue and thus, they can use it in calling or texting on their phones.

Mother tongue was mainly used in communication with people sharing the same ethnicity, for example, when making a phone call: 103/248 comprising 41.53%, when sending text messages: 208/290 comprising 71.72%. In addition to Vietnamese use, respondents employed their mother tongue in calling and texting to their fellow ethnics. As mentioned earlier in 3.2.2, respondents use their mother tongue in in-group communication as this usage makes them act natural, feel comfortable, easy to understand, convenient and create kinship among people with the same ethnicity.

A combination of Vietnamese and mother tongue was mainly found in intergroup communication, for instance, when making a phone call: 63/248 comprising 25.40%, when sending text messages: 8/290 comprising 2.76%. This pattern is mostly applicable to some respondents who are not very fluent in Vietnamese but more competent in their own mother tongue or the language of a major ethnic minority in the region. This usage was more popular in phone calls than in text messages.

Languages of other ethnic minorities mainly found in communication with people sharing the same ethnicity accounted for a smaller proportion compared to other language use patterns, for example, when making a phone call: 6/248 comprising 2.41%, when sending text messages: 5/290 comprising 1.72%

The results from the survey on language use patterns in communication of respondents in some other settings were as follows:

The proportions of respondents using Vietnamese from highest to lowest were: when singing: 245/284 (86.27%), when lulling: 81/268 (33.22%), when speaking to oneself: 55/277 (19.85%). The proportions of respondents using their mother tongue from highest to lowest were: when speaking to oneself: 186/277 (67.15%), when lulling: 91/268 (33.95%), when singing: 12/284 (4.22%). The proportions of respondents using languages of other ethnic groups from highest to lowest were: when lulling: 96/268 (35.82%), when speaking to oneself: 36/277 (13%), when singing: 27/284 (9.5%).

In general, there was a high percentage of respondents using Vietnamese in some personal cases like lulling, self-talking and singing. Except for few respondents who were not taught Vietnamese due to their family and social circumstances, most of them have learnt Vietnamese at school and thus, they can use it in social communication. It is a trend to accept and use the national language of those participants. In addition, their mother tongue was used in personal activities to convey information and emotions to other people and their fellow ethnics, which contributes to preserving cultural values of the community through languages. However, in reality, some respondents do not have a chance to learn their mother tongue. As a result, the use of this language in their personal life is limited. As for the use of languages of other ethnic groups, it depends on personal experience and their self-learning process (They may use the language of a major ethnic group in the region). Therefore, respondents just use the language of other ethnic groups in some specific cases.

Conclusion

The survey examines the patterns of language use in communication by ethnic minority people in Dong Nai province through their proficiency in mother tongue and Vietnamese. Thereby, the picture of language use in family and in social communication among ethnics in the region has been manifested.

Proficiency in mother tongue: Mother tongue is the language of parents' community, passed down from generation to generation during the time of living together. It plays an important role in preserving cultural values and manifesting one's ethnic identity in a most complete way. It is also a popular means of communication in family and in society, being a bridge which helps ethnic minority people to acquire Vietnamese and different types of knowledge effectively. From the survey results, 91.84% of respondents can

speak their mother tongue while only 23.73% of them can write it a little and 15.25% can write fluently. These figures reveal there was a small proportion of respondents who were able to write their mother tongue.

Vietnamese proficiency: Vietnamese is the language of the Vietnamese and also the official language in Vietnam. It is used in nation-wide education, administrative documents and social communication. As a national language, Vietnamese has a higher status in social life compared to languages of other ethnic groups in Vietnam. The results show that 91.79% of respondents can speak Vietnamese and 51.88% of them can write it fluently. These figures reveal that Vietnamese proficiency among ethnic minority people in the region was still low.

Language use in communication among family members: In the case of communication among family members, there was an inverse correlation between the number of respondents who used Vietnamese and their age. On the contrary, a positive correlation was found between the number of respondents using their mother tongue and their age. In communication with visitors of the same ethnicity, respondents' use of mother tongue was proportional to their age while a reverse case was found in the use of Vietnamese. In communication with visitors from other ethnic groups, the national language, Vietnamese, was mainly used by respondents of all age groups in order to achieve communicative effectiveness.

Language use in communication in society: The use of Vietnamese was chosen by above 95% respondents and increased progressively with administrative levels from villages to provinces. In meetings at civil society organizations, this figure exceeded 99%. In regard to language use in the workplace, the percentage of respondents using Vietnamese to communicate with Kinh people and fellow ethnics was high, up to 93%. The proportion of participants using mainly their mother tongue in communication with fellow ethnics in the workplace and public places ranged from 32.51% to 44.94%. Up to 99.33% of respondents used Vietnamese to call and text with Kinh people and people from other ethnic groups. 41.53% of them used their mother tongue in phone calls and 71.72% of them did it in text messages with fellow ethnic. A large rate of respondents, 82.67%, used Vietnamese when singing while 67.15% of them mainly talked to themselves in their mother tongue.

The research results will hopefully provide the government more documentation to issue right policies related to languages, contributing to the preservation and promotion of cultural values through languages for economic development, political stability and security sustainability in the region.

References

- Central Population and Housing Census Steering Committee (2019). *The 2009 Vietnam population and housing census: Completed results*. Statistical Publishing House.
- Vietnam Government Portal. [Tỉnh Đồng Nai nằm trong vùng kinh tế trọng điểm phía Tây, thuộc Đông Nam Bộ. Retrieved October 12, 2020.](#)
- Dong Nai Province Portal. [Tỉnh Đồng Nai nằm ở cực bắc miền Đông Nam Bộ. Retrieved October 12, 2020.](#)
- Nguyen, Thien Giap (2010). *777 khai niệm ngôn ngữ học [777 linguistics concepts]*. Hanoi: Vietnam National University Press
- Nguyen, Minh Hoat (2019). Day song ngu Viet - Ede trong truong tieu hoc o tinh Daklak: Thuc trang va giai phap [Bilingual education of Vietnamese and Ede at primary schools in Daklak Province: Reality and solutions]. *Tap chi Ngon ngu [Journal of Linguistics]*, 4(359), 58-73.
- Nguyen, Van Khang (2011). *Ngon ngu hoc xa hoi [Sociolinguistics]*. Hanoi: Nha xuất bản Giáo dục Việt Nam
- Doan, Van Phuc (2015). *Vấn đề giáo dục tiếng mẹ đẻ đối với cư dân sử dụng một số ngôn ngữ tiểu nhóm Chăm (Gia rai, Raglai, Chu ru) ở Việt Nam hiện nay: thực trạng, giải pháp, kiến nghị 2013-2015. [The current issue of teaching mother tongue to the locals using some languages of Cham ethnic minorities (Gia rai, Raglai, Churu) in Vietnam: Reality, solutions and recommendations 2013-2015]*. A ministry-level science research project led by Linguistic Academy.
- General Statistics Office of Vietnam (2009), *The 2009 Vietnam population and housing census: Completed results*. Statistical Publishing House.

Author Information

Nguyen Minh Hoat

Nguyen Tat Thanh University
300A Nguyen Tat Thanh Street, Ward 13, District 4,
Ho Chi Minh City, Viet Nam

Vu Mai Phuong

University of Finance – Marketing
778 Nguyen Kiem Street, Ward 4, District Phu
Nhuan,
Ho Chi Minh City, Vietnam
